

QualiTePE

Quality of Teaching in Physical Education

Handbook and Guidance Material for the Implementation of the QualiTePE Framework and Instrument

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Technical Sheet

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Website: qualitepe.info

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1 INTRODUCTION

In an era of constant innovation and change, striving for quality and excellence has become crucial. The QualiTePE framework addresses this need, offering a comprehensive approach to improving quality in teaching Physical Education (PE).

This handbook is a practical guide for implementing the QualiTePE framework and instrument, helping to enhance daily teaching practices. It simplifies the complexities of delivering quality Physical Education, providing practical insights, step-by-step guidance, and support to empower individuals, teams, and organizations in achieving excellence in PE. The target groups addressed by the handbook and guidance material include:

- Teacher education institutions;
- Teacher educators;
- Researchers active in the field of teacher education;
- Physical education teachers;
- Physical education student teachers;
- Non-Governmental Organisations like research associations, teacher associations, etc.;
- Stakeholders and policy makers in charge of teacher education.

The QualiTePE framework is not just a set of principles but a holistic system that integrates best practices, proven methodologies, and a mindset of continuous improvement in PE. Whether you are an experienced professional refining existing processes or a new professional establishing a foundation for quality management, this handbook provides the tools, strategies, and understanding needed for successful implementation of QualiTePE.

This handbook combines theoretical rigor with practical applicability, guiding you through the multifaceted aspects of the QualiTePE framework. Explore its contents to embrace a guide that transcends conventional boundaries, fostering innovation, resilience, and adaptability in PE.

In addition to this handbook, we refer to the project website qualitepe.info. Here you will find all information on publications and materials that have been produced in the course of the project.

2 THE QualiTePE PROJECT

In the field of education, the critical importance of teaching quality in shaping student learning and academic success has received significant attention in recent years. Various frameworks have been developed to conceptualize teaching quality, especially in cognitive school subjects (Charalambous & Praetorius, 2020). Identifying the characteristics of effective PE teaching and analyzing their impact on learning is crucial for the field. The UNESCO with their Quality Physical Education (QPE) Policy Project has been described as “one of the most remarkable and significant global initiatives in Physical Education” and describes differences to physical education regarding frequency, variety, inclusivity and value content (McLennan & Thompson, 2015). However, so far there was no consensus in Europe on what constitutes good PE teaching and especially not how to operationalize it.

To address this gap, the collaborative project "QualiTePE," funded by the Erasmus+ programme and involving ten European countries, was launched in 2022. The primary goal was to define the essential criteria for quality teaching in PE, leading to the development of the QualiTePE framework.

This project aimed to conceptualize and operationalize teaching quality in PE by:

1. creating a consensus-based framework defining central teaching dimensions and characteristics in PE,
2. developing a QualiTePE evaluation instrument for formative assessment of PE teaching,
3. providing teaching materials to facilitate an evidence-based implementation of the QualiTePE framework and evaluation instrument in teacher education programmes.

The project brought together experts from different European countries to develop a common understanding of high-quality PE teaching and establish the QualiTePE framework concept. A challenge was that the definition of high-quality PE teaching depended on national educational goals and subject-didactic concepts.

To achieve consensus, a Delphi survey was conducted with experts at different levels in the partner countries, e.g. higher education institutions (HEI) instructors, people with responsibility in educational government within the field of Physical Education Teacher Education (PETE), as well as experienced and qualified mentors or PE teachers, drawing on existing reviews, empirical studies, and curriculum materials. Based on the QualiTePE framework concept, characteristics and dimensions of high quality that include good and effective PE teaching were operationalized, leading to the development of the digital QualiTePE evaluation instrument.

The instrument assesses teaching quality through feedback from teachers, observers, and students on specific teaching characteristics. It underwent iterative validation and revision processes involving partner countries, aiming for consensus among experts.

For the long-term integration of the QualiTePE framework and evaluation instrument in teacher education at HEIs, QualiTePE materials were developed to support instructors in teaching theoretical content and practical implementation. These materials enable pre-service teachers and in-service teachers to reflect on their teaching practice against the QualiTePE framework, providing tools for planning, delivering, and assessing PE lessons based on evidence.

3 THE QualiTePE FRAMEWORK

Since so far there is no general consensus in Europe on what constitutes good PE teaching, the collaborative project "QualiTePE", was undertaken to address this gap in understanding.

3.1 Theoretical starting point

Our first conceptual consideration regarding the development of a subject-specific framework is based on a pre-existing general teaching model, which is called the MAIN-TEACH model (Charalambous & Praetorius, 2020). The MAIN-TEACH model consists of a multi-layered approach to conceptualizing the quality of teaching.

Figure 1

The MAIN-TEACH model (Charalambous & Praetorius, 2020, p. 6)

This model synthesizes international frameworks on teaching quality. It includes both generic and subject-specific aspects comprehensively and multi-layered (see figure 1). Designed around a prototypical teaching-learning sequence, it considers the opportunities-use structure of teaching.

The model comprises eight dimensions across different levels. At the middle layer, it features three basic and generic dimensions of teaching quality: Classroom and time management, Socio-emotional support, and Support for active engagement. The inner layer includes four more dimensions: Selecting and addressing content, Cognitive activation, Supporting practice, and Formative assessment. These layers are organized to support student learning directly. Finally, Differentiation and adaptation is a cutting-across dimension intertwined with all other dimensions (Charalambous & Praetorius, 2020).

We used this model because it reflects current international research on teaching quality and aligns with the subject-didactical discourse on PE teaching quality (e.g., Herrmann & Gerlach, 2020). However, subject-specific adaptations were necessary at the level of subdimensions and indicators.

In conclusion, the MAIN-TEACH model's eight dimensions provided a basis to develop a common understanding of high-quality PE teaching among the European partners.

3.2 The QualiTePE Framework – Presentation of the dimensions and subdimensions

For this purpose, we initiated a cross-cultural Delphi study with 324 PE experts from ten European partner countries. The Delphi process aimed to populate the MAIN-TEACH model with PE-specific content at the level of subdimensions and indicators to reach a consensus. The national expert teams included researchers, PE teacher educators, qualified mentors, and PE teachers with varying levels of experience and expertise.

The Delphi study consisted of three steps:

1. A subgroup of project partners created an initial list of PE-specific content for an adapted framework, reporting on the national status of PE teaching quality.
2. The project experts discussed and revised this content through qualitative communication and subsequent surveys, resulting in an adapted MAIN-TEACH model.
3. National expert teams from all European countries rated the importance and relevance of the proposed content.

Finally, based on the Delphi study results¹, a consensus was reached on a list of six dimensions with subdimensions. Please see the following pages for the dimensions with their subdimensions and the items used from the student perspective.

¹ The manuscript for the Delphi study Langer, W., Scheuer, C., Schnitzler, C., Lefèvre, L., Bailey, R., & Gerlach, E. ([in prep.]). Quality in Physical Education: A European Delphi Study. *Manuscript in preparation*. is currently in preparation and will also be published on the project website.

Table 1 Overview of the QualiTePE dimensions, subdimensions and items

I. Selection and presentation of content and addressing of related objectives	
Clear learning objectives	Our physical education teacher... ... tells us at the beginning of the physical education class what is to be practised. ... tells us what we are supposed to learn in physical education class. ... explains the goals of the physical education class.
Selection of content relevant to students' lives ²	In physical education... ... I offer content that refers to students' life experiences. ... I teach content based on the curriculum. ... I enable my students to have various learning experiences. ... I teach content that is meaningful to the students.
Selection of challenging content	In physical education... ... I can choose different levels of difficulty according to my abilities. ... the physical education teacher chooses content that corresponds to my skill level. ... the physical education teacher allows me to challenge myself.
Comprehensibility	Our physical education teacher... ... explains the exercises in an understandable way. ... gives comprehensive feedback. ... gives clear instructions.
II. Classroom management	
Use of time	In physical education... ... we are always busy. ... we make full use of the time. ... the explanations are brief. ... all materials are ready and accessible at the beginning of the lesson.
Omnipresence	Our physical education teacher... ... immediately notices when someone in the group starts doing something else. ... is aware of everything that happens in the group. ... makes sure that we stay focused throughout the entire physical education class.
Clarity of rules	In physical education... ... we know the rules of conduct that must be followed. ... our physical education teacher explained the consequences of breaking the rules of conduct. ... it is clear what one is allowed and not allowed to do. ... we discuss with the physical education teacher which class rules are important. ... I understand why class rules are needed.
Safety	In physical education... ... our physical education teacher ensures that the safety rules are respected. ... our physical education teacher advises us to handle the material correctly. ... our physical education teacher shows us how to practise the sport safely (e.g., warming up, taking off jewellery).
Dealing with disruptions	In physical education... ... we do not cause many disruptions. ... we listen to the Physical education teacher. ... we behave properly.
III. Socio emotional support and social climate	
Participation	Our physical education teacher... ... lets us help in the design of the exercises. ... responds to our suggestions regarding the content of the physical education classes. ... gives us the opportunity to participate in the organisation of our physical education classes.
Caring	Our physical education teacher... ... pays attention to me. ... takes enough time for me. ... listens to me. ... treats all students equally. ... cares about my problems.

² This sub-dimension is only evaluated from the perspective of observers and teachers. The following questions are formulated for the teacher's perspective.

Encouraging feedback	Our physical education teacher... ... praises me when I improve upon my performance. ... praises students with less competence when they improve themselves. ... praises me when I have performed well. ... provides feedback that encourages me. ... addresses me in an appreciative manner.
IV. Cognitive and motor activation	
Aspiration level	Our physical education teacher implements exercises in which I can show all of my skills. ... implements exercises in which I have to make a real effort. ... implements exercises that challenge me.
Focusing on execution of movement	In physical education... ... I think about how I could learn the new exercises. ... I think beforehand about how to perform the exercises. ... I think about the potential benefit of the exercises for me.
Cognitive processing	In physical education... ... I go through the exercises in my head. ... I try to concentrate on the important points of the exercises. ... I reflect on how well I performed the exercises.
Supporting metacognitive learning	Our physical education teacher... ... asks me to explain how I solved an exercise. ... prompts me to think about how I can approach an exercise. ... asks me to explain how I learned something. ... asks me to describe how I achieved the learning objective.
V. Supporting practice	
Emotional support	Our physical education teacher encourages me to do exercises even better. ... supports me when I make mistakes. ... offers me his/her support.
Differentiation	Our physical education teacher... ... offers us different exercises depending on our abilities. ... lets students who are advancing in class to try more difficult exercises. ... offers students who are not progressing as swiftly to try easier exercises.
Constructive feedback	Our physical education teacher... ... gives me feedback on how to do the exercises correctly. ... shows me how I can do the exercises better. ... gives me helpful feedback.
Structuring	Our physical education teacher draws attention to the important teaching points of the exercises. ... explains the goals of the exercises. ... provides helpful exercises that allow us to further develop myself.
Practise and consolidate content	In physical education... ... I can practise new skills until I master them. ... I can practise where I lack. ... I can practise new skills with different exercises.
Formative assessment	Our physical education teacher tells us how our performance has developed. ... discusses goals with us. ... checks with us whether we have achieved our goals.
VI. Support for active engagement	
On hold	Questions will be developed in the future
Additional Dimension³	
Satisfaction	I am satisfied with how our physical education classes are going. I like the way our physical education teacher organises the lessons. I like our physical education classes.

³ This dimension was not determined in the QualiTePE Delphi study and is more of an outcome than a process characteristic. However, the QUALLIS studies (Herrmann et al., 2023b) identified satisfaction as an important indicator of teaching quality. Aligned with the Delphi study and the validated QUALLIS instrument, this dimension was included as an additional scale.

4 INSTRUCTIONS FOR THE USE OF THE QualiTePE TOOL

4.1 The QualiTePE tool

The QualiTePE tool is constructed upon the previously described consensus-based framework, aimed at guiding the conceptualization of a contemporary and comprehensive understanding of teaching quality in physical education (PE).

The derivation of the items is based both on the described framework and on the previously validated QUALLIS tool (Herrmann et al., 2023).

The tool encapsulates six dimensions of teaching quality, represented through 23 subdimensions⁴ and 78 items⁵. These subdimensions within the QualiTePE instrument are aligned with their respective dimensions within the QualiTePE framework.

The tool is designed to be used by an observer, teacher and students. The observer is someone that watches the lesson(s), either live or on video recording. The teacher is the one whose teaching is being assessed in the tool. The teacher can be a pre-service teacher (initial teacher training) or an in-service teacher (professional development). The students are the ones being taught the lesson(s) by the teacher, for example, primary school pupils, secondary school students, or other pre-service teachers (PE-teacher education students).

Depending on the perspective, the items are tailored to the target person. The individual items, from various perspectives and in different languages, can be found in the [Documentation of Items and Scales](#) (Herrmann et al., 2024).

⁴ A subdimension is a specific category within a broader dimension that groups related items together. It allows for more detailed assessment and analysis of specific aspects of teaching quality within the overall framework. Each subdimension represents a unique characteristic or facet of teaching quality.

⁵ An item is a specific statement or question within a subdimension that respondents evaluate or answer. Items are the building blocks of subdimension, providing the detailed data needed to measure each quality characteristic accurately. There are 78 items in total, distributed across the 23 subdimensions, each contributing to the comprehensive assessment of teaching quality.

4.2 Using the QualiTePE tool in your own setting

The following flowchart gives an overview which steps should be taken when implementing the QualiTePE materials.

Idea Generation

- Choose the learning setting in which you want to implement the QualiTePE materials
- Identify dimensions you would like to focus on

Before starting the lesson, the subdimensions of interest must be selected in the tool. These subdimensions determine which questions will be asked to evaluate the teaching quality. In a PE-teacher education course, these could be pre-selected by the course organizers to reflect the content being taught. Alternatively, a pre-service teacher could select subdimensions that align well with individual learning objectives. An In-service teacher could select subdimensions that have personal relevance, for example out of a perceived need to improve in certain areas, or simply out of curiosity.

Preparation

- Go to: <https://qualitepe.phzh.ch/login/>
- For your first login visit - create your own account
- Prepare your questionnaire

An account is first created via the platform (when conducting the survey for the first time), and then the questionnaire is created. The technical advice on page 17 can provide further support. It is important not to click the 'Submit' button until your participants have fully completed the survey.

Implementation

- Communicate that students/observer need to bring their own devices
- Print out or put on a powerpoint QR codes for students/observers to access the questionnaire
- After the lesson, let your students, observer and yourself adequate time to fill out the questionnaire

Participants answer the questions by clicking on the generated link or the generated QR code.

Evaluation

- In the questionnaire platform click
- Click Symbol to see the questionnaire results
- Interpret the feedback

On the admin user interface of the tool, after clicking Submit, this generates a report consisting of a 'spider web' figure that integrates the scores on all selected subdimensions from all three perspectives (teacher, observer, students). In addition, scores on all the separate items (questions) are shown in bar charts. These results form the basis for reflection and discussion, to generate feedback for further improvement of PE teaching.

4.3 Teaching and learning scenarios

A teaching and learning scenario (TLS) refers to a situation in which the tool can be used for observation and scoring. In fact, every instance in which someone teaches (a part of) a PE lesson can serve as a TLS.

To provide an overview or some ideas of situations in which the tool can be used, an indicative collection of didactic scenarios has been compiled.

4.3.1 Teaching and learning scenarios for PE teacher education:

1. **Micro-Teaching Discussion with Peers:** As part of a unit for beginning teacher education students, the tool is applied in a micro-teaching situation where the (student) teacher teaches one lesson phase with a specific focus to a small group of fellow students. One other student is assigned the role of observer and does not participate in the lesson. All participants subsequently discuss the results. Because there is no expert involved in this situation, this TLS serves mainly to help all students think about what quality PE teaching actually is. This objective should be explained beforehand, to avoid putting too much pressure on the student teacher. An expert (PE teacher educator) can subsequently review the discussion of the group and answer any questions that have arisen from it.

2. **Micro-Teaching Discussion Facilitation by Expert:** This TLS describes the same situation as the first, but now with an expert observer, such as a PE teacher educator. The objective is still to help the students think about what quality PE teaching is. The expert can lead the discussion e.g., by giving examples of the different dimensions and clarify any misconceptions about quality PE teaching as they arise. The expert should stimulate an open discussion between students and not put too much emphasis on the scores given as an expert.

3. **Classroom Observation with Subsequent Reflection Opportunity:** In this TLS, the objective is improving the PE teaching of an individual PE-student. A student-teacher teaches (part of) a lesson to fellow-students. A teacher educator serves as the observer, and discusses the results obtained with the tool individually with the student-teacher. In later phases of the initial teacher education, when students are more experienced and have a better comprehension of teaching quality, this role of observer might also be taken by a fellow student.

4. **Classroom Observation in School with Subsequent Reflection Opportunity:** During school placement, a student-teacher teaches (part of) a lesson to the pupils/students. The observer is either a visiting university teacher educator or a PE teacher supervising the student-teacher in school. A variation on this could be that both the university teacher and school supervisor act as observers. In that manner, not only the student-teacher but also both observers get to refine their thinking about what is quality PE.

4.3.2 Teaching and learning scenarios for in-service teachers:

1. **Individualized Instructional Development:** A PE teacher reviews the QualiTePE dimensions and subdimensions, reflecting on areas for personal improvement. After selecting the relevant subdimensions, the teacher teaches one or several lessons and the students respond to the corresponding items in the tool. The aim of this is to check whether school students' scores confirm the perception that these subdimensions deserve further attention. If so, the PE teachers plan lessons to experiment with improving teaching. Subsequently, a TLS is planned where a colleague, mentor, or other expert acts as an observer.

2. **Instructional Development as a Team:** A PE department or subgroup of PE teachers form a learning community. They plan a series of observations where one teacher observes another, and students also score the lesson quality through the tool. By systematically exploring several or all dimensions of the QualiTePE framework, the learning community decides on which subdimension(s) are most interesting to focus on. Together they develop teaching strategies to improve the chosen subdimension(s), and plan for lessons to implement this in. By repeatedly using the QualiTePE tool (possibly using video observation), they iteratively improve the quality of PE teaching in school.

3. **Instructional Development in Professional Development Sessions:** During professional development meetings, PE teachers could use the QualiTePE tool when teaching, taking part in or observing a lesson organized for the meeting. By discussing the outcomes with peers, the QualiTePE framework and tool will be disseminated, benefiting teaching quality.

4.4 Set up your QualiTePE Questionnaire

The following description will help you to create your own QualiTePE online questionnaire. A more detailed description, including information on data protection, can be found in the [QualiTePE technical manual](#) (Crapa et al., 2024).

1. Registration

1. Go to the QualiTePE homepage: qualitepe.phzh.ch

Start the registration process with the link on the homepage. A questionnaire will guide you through the registration process.

After registration, an initialisation email will be sent to you. If you have not received the mail, check your spam and junk mail inbox.

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Quality of teaching and learning in physical education.

E-Mail

Password

Not registered yet? Register here

Change password / Forgot password

Sign-in

2. Change your password if necessary

1. In the Library window, click "Profile" in the top right-hand corner.
2. Create your own password. Click on the "Save" button.

The password must contain:

- At least 8 characters
- At least one upper case character
- At least one lower case character
- At least one number

3. Create a survey

1. In the Library tab, click on the green button "Start Survey".

QualiTePE - Quality of Teaching in Physical Education

Evaluation tool to assess the quality of teaching in physical education. Theoretically based on the QualiTePE framework concept.

2. Enter data and information about the survey in window 1 "Survey Data".

ATTENTION: The collection of data must be anonymised. This means that no names, addresses or personal details of persons may be entered under the item "Name of survey"!

Click on the green button "Next".

Step 1 - Survey Data

Creator

Ronja Räubertochter

Selected template

QualiTePE - Quality of Teaching in Physical Education

Name of Survey

Please enter a name for the survey. This name will appear in the survey overview.

Please note that the surveys must be anonymised for data protection reasons. I.e. do not use names, addresses, age details etc. to name the survey.

3. In window 2 "Questionnaire", an overview of the 23 QualiTePE subdimensions is provided. To learn more about the items behind each subdimension, you can hover your cursor over the respective items. Select at least three subdimensions for your survey. A maximum of eight quality characteristics can be selected. The less subdimensions are selected, the better is the focus of all participants and the easier and more precise the judgment. Click on the green button "Next".

Please select the quality dimensions to be evaluated.

- | | | | |
|---|---|---|--|
| ☐ Selection of content relevant to students' lives | ☐ Omnipresence | ☐ Structuring | ☐ Focusing on execution of movement |
| ☐ Selection of challenging content | ☐ Safety | ☐ Comprehensibility | ☐ Cognitive processing |
| ☐ Clear learning objectives | ☐ Caring | ☐ Aspiration level | ☐ Supporting metacognitive learning |
| ☐ Clarity of rules | ☐ Emotional support | ☐ Differentiation | ☐ Formative assessment |
| ☐ Use of time | ☐ Satisfaction | ☐ Practise and consolidate content | ☐ Dealing with disruptions |
| | ☐ Participation | ☐ Constructive feedback | |
| | ☐ Encouraging feedback | | |

4. In window 3 "Summary" the survey links for the students, for the teaching PE teachers and for the observers are displayed. These links must be shared with the respective groups of people. The links can also be shared via the respective QR codes. To do this, save the QR codes with a right mouse click and share them as a printed image or as a beamer projection. Close the window using the cross at the top right. The QR codes and the links can also be downloaded directly as a PDF document.

ATTENTION: Do not select "Submit". This closes the survey. A closed survey cannot be opened again. Close the window using the cross at the top right.

Below you will find the links for your survey. Share the links or the corresponding QR codes with the appropriate target group (e.g. share link and QR code students with the class to be surveyed).

The QR codes and the links can be downloaded as a PDF document. Please use the function Download QR codes and links:

[QR codes and links PDF Download](#)

Property	Value
Survey Name	Manual demo
Survey links	

Survey Name	Manual demo		
Survey links			
Student	https://sula.pro/th5thqfi 		
Teacher	https://sula.pro/xcjz3mci	Observer	https://sula.pro/3o7wiuut

5. Surveys can be downloaded as PDF files and printed out. To do this, select the corresponding link and click on it. The survey is loaded. In the survey window, the questionnaire can be downloaded under "Download questionnaire as PDF".

- 8
- 9
- 10
- 11
- 12
- 13
- 14
- 15
- 16
- 17
- 18 or older

[Download questionnaire as PDF](#)

Safety

In physical education...

	strongly disagree	disagree	neither/nor agree	agree	strongly agree	I do not know.
our physical education teacher ensures that the safety rules are respected.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
our physical education teacher advises us to handle the material correctly.	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐
our physical education teacher shows us how to practice the sport safely (e.g., warming up, taking off jewellery).	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐	☐

4. Closing and evaluating the survey

1. In the Library window, choose "Survey results" and click on "Current Surveys".

Select the survey to be completed and evaluated. The surveys can be filtered by creation ID, survey name and status. Select the pencil icon on the right.

CTPE Quality Library Survey results Ronja Räubertochter (Observer)

Current Surveys

Id	Survey name	State	Survey Creator	Survey Template	Actions
57	Manual demo	ACTIVE	Ronja Räubertochter	QualiTePE - Quality of Teaching in Physical Education	
56		COMPLETED	Ronja Räubertochter	QualiTePE - Quality of Teaching in Physical Education	

Page 1 of 1 (2 items)

- In window 3 "Summary" the survey can be closed by clicking on the green button "Submit". The survey may only be closed once all respondents (pupils, PE teacher, observer) have answered the respective questionnaire.

In order to complete the survey, you must confirm this step with the control question:
 "I understand that the green area "Submit" finally closes the survey. A completed survey is evaluated and can no longer be changed afterwards."

ATTENTION: Once a survey has been closed, it cannot be opened again.

1 SURVEY > 2 QUESTIONNAIRE > 3 SUMMARY

English

By clicking on the green "Submit" button, the survey is finally closed and the evaluation is calculated. The survey may only be closed once all respondents (pupils, sports teacher, observer) have answered the respective questionnaire. ATTENTION: Once a question has been closed, it cannot be opened again.

This window can be closed by clicking on the green cross at the top right.

I understand that the green area "Submit" finally closes the survey. A completed survey is evaluated and can no longer be changed afterwards.

Step 3 - Summary

← Back Submit →

5. Analysis of the surveys

1. In the Survey results window, click on the "evaluate" icon for the current survey

Current Surveys

Id	Survey name	State	Survey Creator	Survey Template	Actions
57	Manual demo	COMPLETED	Ronja Räubertochter	QualiTePE - Quality of Teaching in Physical Education	
56	tt	COMPLETED	Ronja Räubertochter	QualiTePE - Quality of Teaching in Physical Education	

Page 1 of 1 (2 items)
< 1 >

2. In the window "Overview of the selected quality characteristics", the mean values of the three perspectives - pupils, PE teacher and observer (s) - are shown in colour in a spider diagram.

3. In the evaluation window "Overview of the selected quality characteristics", the answers to the three perspectives of pupils, sports teacher and observer(s) are shown as a bar chart under the spider diagram.

4. In the evaluation window "Overview of the selected quality characteristics", the report can be downloaded as a PDF by clicking on the button "download report as pdf".

download report as pdf

5 DISCUSSING THE QualiTePE RESULTS

Feedback and the QualiTePE tool

It is important to realize that the QualiTePE tool is a starting point for the feedback process. Often, the three perspectives (i.e., teacher, student and observer) obtained through the tool will result in different scores. This highlights that, as with all observations, the quantitative scores are open to interpretation. It is exactly this interpretation, and the discussion of it, that can help to generate valuable qualitative feedback. Before providing suggestions specifically for the use of the QualiTePE tool, we will describe a few basic general principles about feedback.

- Feedback should be targeted, specific and clear. To achieve this, it helps to keep in mind three basic questions, that are considered central to formative assessment strategies:
 - a) What is the goal of the lesson?
 - b) How is the learner performing?
 - c) How can the learner improve his/her performance?

In this case, the learner is the person teaching the PE lesson to students. If the learner does not know what quality PE looks like (question a), it will be difficult to improve. The QualiTePE framework with its dimensions, subdimensions and items, provides information about this. Therefore, it is important that both the observer and teacher know and understand the tool, especially the subdimensions chosen for the specific lesson.

Subsequently, the learner should have information about the current level of performance (question b). This is the information provided by the QualiTePE tool, from three different perspectives.

However, without additional information, such as strategies to improve (question c), feedback will be ineffective. This is why it is important to follow up the assessment done with the QualiTePE tool, and the data this provides, with an interpretation and discussion, aimed at improvement. Feedback generated during this process should be clearly related to achieving success on the predetermined subdimensions, otherwise it will not be effective.

Finally, research shows that feedback is less effective when it is perceived as a threat to self-esteem. This is possibly because people are incapable of paying full attention to the content of the feedback when they feel pressure. Therefore, it is important to create suitable conditions in which the observed teacher feels supported and feedback is discussed in a constructive way (Monteiro et al., 2021), because the sole objective is to (further) improve teaching and not to be judgmental.

Key points when using the QualiTePE-tool for feedback:

- Make sure that all involved (different roles) have a correct understanding of the QualiTePE framework.
- Select one or more subdimension of interest.
- Provide feedback that is targeted, specific and clear. Keep in mind following three questions:
 - What is the goal?
 - How is the learner doing?
 - How can the learner improve?
- Create conditions in which the observed teacher feels supported, not judged.

As a general outline, when the teacher and observer(s) discuss the results from the tool after the lesson(s), we recommend the following steps:

1. Discuss the dimensions with the **HIGHEST values** from all perspectives. This serves towards the reinforcement of teacher's strengths, and sets a positive, appreciative stage for the rest of the discussion.
2. Discuss the dimensions with **LOW values** from all perspectives. The objective of this is to aim for improvement in areas that require further development. During this phase, the three basic questions of formative assessment mentioned above can be used as a guide.
3. Discuss the dimensions with **obvious differences** between scores. This helps the teacher and observer(s) to understand each other's perspectives. It may also help to clear up differences in comprehension of the subdimensions and how these translate into practice.

A rule of thumb is to, in each step, let the teachers reflect on the score they assigned to themselves first. For example, a starting question could be: 'why did you give yourself two

points for ... *[insert a subdimension]*'. The observers can ask clarifying (but not judgemental) questions after this. The observers then add their perspective and bring into the discussion the scores obtained from the students.

Please remember to use the results from the tool as a starting point for reflection. Given that observation involves interpretation of both the items in the subdimensions as well as the teachers' behaviour, there is always a fair amount of subjectivity involved. The resulting differences in scores should be seen to engage in a meaningful, concrete, and developmentally aimed conversation. Not as an absolute 'grade' for teacher performance.

To facilitate appreciative and sustainable feedback, you can follow these points:

- Consider the feedback setting (e.g. initial teacher education, school peer feedback) and levels of expertise involved (e.g. peer feedback, expert to novice feedback);
- Aim to address both feedback (what was done) and feedforward (what can be done);
- Contextualise the "score" in relative terms of a "perspective of teaching";
- Only refer to "formative assessment" when referring to initial teacher education / preservice teachers;
- At all times, aim to focus on the general aspect of "feedback" that applies both to in service and pre-service for the purpose of collaboration;
- Use the matrix of Brooks et al focusing on "feedback strategies" to expand with a brief explanation and an example (page 28). The feedback matrix aims to bridge theory and practice by providing practical examples and strategies for teachers at each feedback type and level, emphasizing the ongoing interaction between feedback types rather than viewing them as sequential steps (Brooks et al., 2019).

Table 2 Matrix of feedback for Learning (Brooks et al., 2019)

Learner Stage	Feedback Level	Feeding Up: Where am I going?	Feeding Back: How am I going?	Feeding Forward: What do I have to do next?	
Novice	Task	<p>Feeding Up Prompts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Today we are learning... • Success in this task will look like...(exemplar/model) • The key criteria for success are... • We are looking for... <p>Feedback Strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce complexity • Use exemplars/models • Identify misconceptions • Use diagnostic assessment for goal setting 	<p>Feedback Prompts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • You have/haven't met the learning intention by... • You have/haven't met the success criteria by... • Your answer/work is/isn't what we are looking for because... <p>Feedback Strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Avoid over emphasis of error analysis • Feedback must be immediate • Match feedback to success criteria 	<p>Feed Forward Prompts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To fully meet the learning intention, you could... • Addressing the following success criteria would improve your work... • Adding/removing ___would improve your work. <p>Feed Forward Strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use language from the success criteria • Use scaffolding • Feed Forward must be timely • Use challenge • Refer to goals 	
	Proficient	Process	<p>Feeding Up Prompts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The key ideas/concepts in this task are... • These ideas/concepts are related by... • Key questions you could ask about this task are... • Skills you will need in this task are... • Strategies you will need in this task are... <p>Feeding Up Strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use graphical organisers • Reduce scaffolding • Increase complexity • Use mastery goals 	<p>Feedback Prompts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Your understanding of the ideas/concepts within this task is... • Your thinking about this task is... • You demonstrated ___skills to a ___ level. • You used ___strategies to a ___ level. <p>Feedback Strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feedback amount can start to increase • Feedback complexity can increase • Use prompts or cues 	<p>Feed Forward Prompts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • You could improve your understanding of ___concepts by... • Thinking further about ___could improve your work by... • You could improve your ___skills by... <p>Feed Forward Strategies</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Feed Forward amount can start to increase • Feed Forward complexity can increase • Use prompts or cues • Use challenge
	Advanced	Self-Regulatory	<p>Feeding Up Prompts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How will you use the learning intention? • How could you use the success criteria? • Which other ways could you monitor your work? <p>Feeding Up Strategies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduce emphasis of exemplars • Mastery and performance goals 	<p>Feedback Prompts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are you on track with your work? • How do you know? • To which level are you satisfying the success criteria? • Are you on track to achieving your goal? • How do you know? <p>Feedback Strategies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delay feedback • May only require verification feedback 	<p>Feed Forward Prompts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How could you deepen your understandings? • How could you improve your work? • What is the next step for your learning? • How do you know? <p>Feed Forward Strategies:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delay feedback • Reduce teacher reliance • Develop self-regulated learners

6 CONCLUSION

We hope this QualiTePE handbook serves as a valuable and practical resource for university lecturers and physical education teachers. By using the QualiTePE materials, you can enhance the quality of your physical education programs and contribute to the development of effective teaching practices. We encourage you to explore the various strategies and examples provided and to adapt them to fit your individual educational contexts.

For additional resources and publications from the project, please visit our website at QualiTePE.info, where you will find a wealth of information to support your ongoing professional development. You will find links to different publications, a detailed [technical manual](#), and the [scale documentation](#) with all the dimensions and items in detail. These materials as well as this handbook are available in various languages on the website, providing accessible support for educators around Europe and beyond.

The QualiTePE project team is dedicated to fostering quality in physical education, and we are confident that these materials will inspire and empower you to achieve this goal. We wish you much joy and success as you implement and further develop high-quality physical education practices. If you have any questions or suggestions, please feel free to contact the project team (page 31).

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